

Site: SPHINX
TEMPLE Season GS 79-80

Area: N. COLONNADE Square R16 Locus Number 4c

Progress of Excavation 10/I/80: After removing - trimming, to balk
4, 4a-4b (Separately), cleared 4c: down to surface 4d
13/I/80: 4c trimmed back to balk line as w/ 4-4b-4c; 13/I/80
scraped down 4c to the surface of 4d;

Locus Description "BROWN SAND, STONE RUBBLE" Granite, Dolerite,
Alabaster Frags, Carbon spots (some fairly large), grey alluvial
mud spots, large pieces limestone, and many smaller frags.
Some gypsum inclusions

Location in Square NE Corner as 4-4b

Under Locus 4b LIGHT BUFF CLAY-
gypsum Over Locus 4d Mottled grey sand
- gypsum

Locus Dimensions 15-20 cm thick

Levels _____

Analysis of non-artifactual materials One small finished frag of
alabaster came up in trimming E Balk - 4c. - Flat face